

पेटेंट कार्यालय
शासकीय जर्नल

**OFFICIAL JOURNAL
OF
THE PATENT OFFICE**

निर्गमन सं. 02/2023
ISSUE NO. 02/2023

शुक्रवार
FRIDAY

दिनांक: 13/01/2023
DATE: 13/01/2023

पेटेंट कार्यालय का एक प्रकाशन
PUBLICATION OF THE PATENT OFFICE

(54) Title of the invention : MACHINE LEARNING APPROACH FOR ESTIMATION OF GENETIC DIVERSITY AND PHYTOCHEMICAL CONSTITUENT ACTIVITIES IN PIPER BETLE L. LEAVE VARIETIES BASED ON MORPHOLOGICAL AND MOLECULAR MARKERS

(51) International classification :A61K0036670000, C12Q0001689500, A01H0005120000, G16C0020700000, G06K0009620000

(86) International Application No :PCT//
Filing Date :01/01/1900

(87) International Publication No : NA

(61) Patent of Addition to Application Number :NA
Filing Date :NA

(62) Divisional to Application Number :NA
Filing Date :NA

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(57) Abstract :

Machine learning approach for estimation of genetic diversity and phytochemical constituent activities in Piper betle L. leave varieties based on morphological and molecular markers is the proposed invention. The proposed invention used morphological markers like leaf length, leaf width, and petiole size. By using the morphological markers, hierarchical cluster analysis was carried out, which grouped these four cultivars into two major clusters. In molecular marker analysis, a total of ten RAPD primers used, generating 43 number of amplified bands. Among them, 15 number of polymorphic bands and seven unique bands were found. The genetic diversity and relatedness among the four cultivars were computed using Jaccard's similarity coefficient. The dendrogram grouped all the four cultivars into two main clusters. This RAPD banding patterns can be useful for genetic diversity studies, for cultivar selection, and to marker assist breeding programs. Phytochemical similarities and differences among the species were characterised through multivariate analyses approaches. Principal component analysis based on the relative abundance of phytochemicals, indicated that the betel cultivars could be grouped into three groups. Our results of FTIR, GC-MS and NMR based profiling combined with multivariate analyses suggest that untargeted metabolomics can play a crucial role in documenting metabolic signatures of endemic betel leaf varieties

No. of Pages : 24 No. of Claims : 4